
Deliverable D1.2.3
Pilot PT on outbreak
surveillance based on
WGS data

Work package 1, Task 2,
ST3

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: DTU, SSI, UCM,
APHA, PIWET, ISS, RIVM, WBVR, SLV,
FOHM, SVA, ANSES

Other participants: Singapore Food
Agency

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

JIP/JRP deliverable	D1.2.3 Pilot PT on outbreak surveillance based on WGS data		
Project Acronym	CARE		
Authors	Jeppe Boel, Pernille Gympoese, Sally Hallam, Paula Johnson, Mia Torpdahl		
Other contributors	Angela van Hoek, Anniina Jaakkonen, Ásgeir Ástvaldsson, Chng Kern Rei and Lim Jia Qi, Gianni Ciccaglioni, Jette Sejer Kjeldgaard, Joakim Skarin, Juris Kibilds, Laetitia Bonifait, Laura Villa, Liljana Petrovska, Magdalena Zajac, Malgorzata Ligowska-Marzeta, Maroua Sayeb, Nadja Karamehmedovic, Raquel Abad Torreblanca, Silvia Herrera León, Suvi Wallgren, Taru Lienemann, Valérie Rose		
Due month of the report	58		
Actual submission month	60		
Type	R <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.;</i> <i>OTHER</i>		
Dissemination level	PU <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>		
Dissemination	OHEJP WP 1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.			

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

	<p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p><u>Other recipient(s):</u></p>
--	--

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

PILOT PT ON OUTBREAK SURVEILLANCE BASED ON WGS DATA

A CROSS-SECTORIAL PILOT PROFICIENCY TEST (PT)/EXTERNAL QUALITY ASSESSMENT (EQA) ON CLUSTER DETECTION OF FOOD-BORNE PATHOGENS BASED ON WHOLE GENOME SEQUENCING

1. Terms and definitions

APHA	Animal & Plant Health Agency
cgMLST	Core genome MultiLocus Sequence Typing
FWD	Food- and Waterborne Diseases
EQA	External Quality Assessment
MLST	Multi Locus Sequence Typing
OH	One health
PT	Proficiency Test
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
SSI	Statens Serum Institut
ST	Sequence Type
wgMLST	Whole genome MultiLocus Sequence Typing
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

2. Summary

A cross-sectorial *in silico* based pilot proficiency test (PT) or external quality assessment for identification of outbreak associated clusters food borne pathogenic bacteria was organised with participants from the public health, veterinary and food sector. The participants were asked to analyse whole genome sequences (WGSs) generated from three species, *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*. The sequences were distributed as FASTQ files.

A total of 15 institutions represented by 20 participants with unique contact persons signed up for the PT. Thirteen of the 20 participants represented the food and veterinary sector, four the public health sector and three represented both the public health and the food/veterinary sector.

Genome sequences were provided using a secure-FTP (sFTP) site and included 35, 27 and 31 genome sequences of *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*, together with a document with practical guidance.

The participants were asked to use their current WGS analysis pipeline for analysis, and include an evaluation of the quality of the sequences. For WGSs with a satisfactory quality, sequence type (ST), species for *Campylobacter* and serotype for *Salmonella* should be extracted and reported. The participants were further asked to identify samples that clustered together and to report allele- and/or SNP-differences to predefined index samples. Additionally the participants were asked to provide information on their applied analytical methods including their cut-off for cluster detection. The results reported by the participants were compared to the results generated by the PT-provider, and individual reports with feedback on the concordance were provided to each of the participants.

The participants applied a range of different tools for analysis and were overall able to correctly determine the quality of the genome sequences and identify the correct species, serotype and ST. In general, the participants were also able to identify the clusters of closely related sequences for all three species, and the submitted results were in concordance with the results from the PT-provider. There were not identified cross-sectorial differences in concordance of the reported results.

An important conclusion from this pilot PT is that it is possible to use a cross-sectorial approach for assessment of the One Health capacity to characterise and detect clusters among food-borne pathogens based on WGS. The further development of WGS based cluster detection PTs requires a multidisciplinary approach and require skills from the laboratory side as well as programming and computational skills. It is important that the work is undertaken internationally so it is ensured that the new tools are applicable worldwide, It is also important, that the responsible national and international bodies are supporting the area with resources in order to facilitate the development of methodologies and harmonization of the area. Once the PTs are in place it will be straightforward to conduct cross sectorial one-health based PTs as this only will require that the laboratories from the different sectors sign up for the same PTs.

3. Background

Whole genome sequencing (WGS) and the on-going development of tools for analysis of genome sequences has greatly improved the possibility for phylogenetic and population structure analysis of bacteria. Genome sequences are used routinely in many countries for surveillance of foodborne infections, including *Salmonella*, *Campylobacter* and *Listeria monocytogenes*. The surveillance include cluster analysis for detection of closely related isolates and identification of possible outbreaks. WGS-based techniques are also used for general epidemiological investigations, including source attribution studies, for improvement of the understanding of the epidemiology and the possibility of control of pathogens in the food chain.

The OH-EJP CARE project aims at developing proficiency testing (PT)/External Quality Assurance (EQA) schemes to assess the combined performance of the one health (OH)-sector. The aim of conducting this *in silico* based cross-sectorial PT was to assess OH-laboratories ability to identify clusters of isolates based on WGS. An additional aim was to identify parameters for improving the quality of future cross sectorial WGS-based cluster detection PTs and to provide recommendations for the design of future cross-sectorial PTs within the area.

4. Introduction

WGS is an effective method for characterization of foodborne pathogens, and WGS-based techniques are widely adopted among public health, food and veterinary institutions for surveillance of foodborne pathogens. WGS can be used to obtain information about the foodborne isolates with regard to species, serotype, sequence type (ST), antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes. Genome sequences are also used to establish the clonal relationship between isolates of the same species, including foodborne bacteria like *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*.

For determination of clonal relationship two different approaches are widely used, namely core/whole genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST/wgMLST) or single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). The recognition of closely related isolates by identifying clusters of sequences are of major importance in surveillance of foodborne pathogens for identification of potential outbreaks.

The rapid development of new tools for analysis and comparison of genome sequences is challenging from a harmonization standpoint. When WGS-based techniques are applied for surveillance of foodborne outbreaks it is crucial that the identification of clusters, that potentially can be outbreak related, are identified and communicated, and that appropriate measures are undertaken in order to manage the outbreak. In this context cluster identification is the primary focus, whereas the methods that are applied for cluster detection are secondary as long as the same clusters are being identified.

The objective of this PT scheme was to assess the ability of the participants to detect clusters of genetically closely related isolates of *Campylobacter*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*. The PT was divided into three schemes, one for each pathogen, and organized as an *in silico* exercise. The participants received samples in the form of FASTQ files from the Illumina sequencing technology. The participants were requested to use their current/routine pipeline to analyse the genome sequences and identify clusters of closely related sequences within each of the three pathogens. The participants were further requested to indicate whether the sequences passed their routine quality assurance procedure and indicate, whenever relevant, the species, serotype and ST. Finally the participants were asked to provide information on their analytical approach. The submitted results were analyzed and compared with the results of the PT-provider and individual feedback were given to each of the participants.

The experiences from the pilot PT was used to identify parameters where improvements could be made, and thus improve the quality of future cross sectorial WGS-based cluster detection PTs.

5. Outline of the proficiency test

5.1. WGS analysis performed by the PT-provider

The PT included genome sequences from 35, 27, and 31 isolates of *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, and *Salmonella*, respectively. The isolates were selected among the routine isolates received at Statens Serum Institute (SSI) in its capacity as the national public health institute and responsible for the national surveillance of human foodborne infections in Denmark.

The genome sequences included in the PT were selected based on QC-parameters, species designation, serotype when relevant, ST and cluster analysis as outlined below.

Single colonies were used to extract genomic DNA with an enzymatic pre-lysis step prior to automated purification using the MagNA Pure 96 DNA and Viral NA Small Volume Kit and DNA Blood ds SV 2.0 protocol (Roche Diagnostics, Hvidovre, Denmark). Libraries were constructed, and sequencing was performed using the Nextera XT Kit (Illumina, Little Chesterford, United Kingdom) and 300-cycle kits on the NextSeq 550 (Illumina) platform according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Quality control of the sequences data was done using bifrost (<https://github.com/ssi-dk/bifrost>). Sequences were further analysed using species specific cgMLST schemes ((*Salmonella* EnteroBase (<https://doi.org/10.1371%2Fjournal.pgen.1007261>), *L.monocytogenes*: Institut Pasteur (Nature Microbiology (2016) 2:16185), *Campylobacter*: Oxford (<https://doi.org/10.1128/jcm.00080-17>)) in BioNumerics 8.1 (BioMérieux, Belgium).

A cgMLST related cluster was defined by the population structure in the relevant ST applying single linkage clustering or a minimum spanning tree (MS) in Bionumerics. Clusters of closely related isolates were defined using cluster cut-offs of 3 alleles for *Salmonella*, 5 alleles for *Campylobacter* and 7 alleles for *Listeria*.

SNPs were detected using the NASP pipeline (Sahl JW et al. Microb genomics. 2016;2(8):e000074). SNPs were called against a denovo-assembled genome of the same ST among the CARE sequences using BWA-MEM and GATK. Recombination events were removed from the SNP data using three different methods – CleanRecomb (GitHub - ssi-dk/CleanRecomb: Cleans putative recombination events from a SNP matrix), ClonalFrame (<https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.106.063305>) and Gubbins (<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gku1196>). SNP trees were calculated in Bionumerics using the maximum parsimony approach for identification of closely related sequences. Clusters of closely related isolates were defined using cluster cut-offs of 5 SNPs for *Salmonella*, 7 SNPs *Campylobacter* and 10 SNPs for *Listeria*.

For each species one sequence was manipulated so it failed the SSI quality control (QC) pipeline. One *Campylobacter* sample was contaminated with DNA from two different *Campylobacter* isolates; one *Listeria monocytogenes* sample failed QC due to a low read coverage, and one *Salmonella* sample was contaminated with DNA from another species.

After selection all non-manipulated samples were anonymised in order to comply with the general data protection regulation in the European Union. The anonymised samples were renamed CARE001 to CARE105, reanalyzed, and the results of these analyses were the results established by the PT-provider. All anonymised sequences were deposited to the European Nucleotide Archive (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>; Submission SUB11781156 Bioproject PRJNA857551).

5.2. Recruitment of participants

The pilot PT participants were recruited among the partner institutions of the OH EJP CARE project. Additionally the Singapore Food Agency participated. Following a series of EJP-CARE meetings, where the concept of the pilot PT was introduced, all potential participants were officially invited to take part in the PT with an e-mail sent from SSI on November 26 2021. The e-mail contained overall information about the PT and a link to a web based survey tool (www.analyzer.com), where the participants could sign up, provide contact information, and indicate in which part(s) of the PT (*Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes*, or *Salmonella* scheme) the institution would participate. In the invitation e-mail it was further mentioned, that more details would be provided when the list of participating institutes, including contact persons, were consolidated. It was also announced that a teleconference was going to take place on 9 December 2021 prior to the launch of the PT, to clarify any outstanding issues.

A total of 15 institutions represented by 20 participants with unique contact persons signed up for the PT. Thirteen of the 20 participants represented the food and veterinary sector, four the public health sector and three represented both the public health and the food/veterinary sector.

All 15 institutions participated in the teleconference held on December 9th, 2021.

Table 1. Institutions that participated in the pilot PT on cluster detection. Some institutions participated with more than one participant

Institution	<i>Salmonella</i> method	<i>Campylobacter</i> method	<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> method
Statens Serum Institut, Denmark	Allele based	Allele based	Allele based
Public Health Agency of Sweden	SNP	SNP	SNP
Animal & Plant Health Agency, United Kingdom	SNP	SNP	SNP
ANSES Laboratory for Food Safety, France		Allele based	
Finnish Food Authority		Allele based	
ANSES Ploufragan, France	SNP		
RIVM, the Netherlands	Allele based	Allele based	Allele based
Swedish Food Agency	SNP	SNP	SNP
Institute of Food Safety, "BIOR", Spain	Allele based	Allele based	Allele based
Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Spain	Allele based	Allele based	Allele based
ANSES Ploufragan, France			
PIWET, Poland	Allele based		
Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy	Allele based	Allele based	
Finnish Food Authority	Allele based		
SVA, National Veterinary Institute, Sweden	SNP	Allele based	
Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy			Allele based
Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Spain			Allele based
Singapore Food Agency	SNP	SNP	SNP
Finnish Food Authority			Allele based
DTU - National Food Institute, Denmark	SNP	SNP	SNP
Number of laboratories	14	13	12

5.3. Distribution of PT schemes, analysis and feedback

Instructions and all DNA sequences in FASTQ format were uploaded to a secure File Transfer Protocol site (sFTP-site) hosted by SSI. The PT was launched on 15 December 2021, where all contact persons, received an e-mail with instructions. Also on 15 December 2021, all contact persons were contacted by e-mail, and created as users on the sFTP-site with personal log on credentials.

On the sFTP-site, sequences from each species were provided in separate folders. The participants downloaded the relevant instructions and WGSs and they were asked to use their routine set-up for analysis of the sequence data.

For each scheme the participants were asked to provide general information on the applied methods. The participants that applied MLST-based approaches were asked to provide information about the platform/tool used for allele analysis (e.g. BioNumerics, SeqSphere, DIGS db-Lm), allele calling method (e.g. assembly based, mapping based), allele assembler (e.g. SPAdes, Velvet), allele analysis scheme, number of loci in the allelic scheme, and number of allele-differences used as cut-off for calling a cluster/outbreak.

The participants that applied SNP-based approaches were asked to provide information about the used reference genome, SNP-pipeline and analytical approach, assembler, variant caller and number of SNP-differences used as cut-off for calling a cluster.

For all samples the participants should report the result of their QC (acceptable, yes/no), and if the quality was unacceptable the participants could indicate the reason why. The participants should report, depending on pathogen, the species, serotype and ST, and further indicate if they considered a sample as part of a cluster (yes/no). For specific STs of each pathogens, the participants were asked perform ST-specific cluster analysis and report the allele- and/or SNP-distance to predefined index samples defined by the provider of the PT.

For *Campylobacter*, cluster analysis should be done for each of these STs:

ST19 (use CARE041 as index sample)
ST21 (use CARE052 as index sample)
ST22 (use CARE074 as index sample)
ST50 (use CARE063 as index sample)
ST257 (use CARE027 as index sample)
ST872 (use CARE060 as index sample)
ST872 (use CARE060 as index sample)

For *L. monocytogenes*, cluster analysis should be done for each of these STs:

ST1 (use CARE042 as index sample)
ST8 (use CARE039 as index sample)
ST391 (use CARE002 as index sample)
ST451 (use CARE044 as index sample)

For *Salmonella*, cluster analysis should be done for each of these STs:

ST10 (CARE86 index sample)
ST11 (CARE9 index sample)
ST19 (CARE11 index sample)
ST34 (CARE15 index sample)

A customized version of the standard PT communication and reporting platform hosted by the Veterinary Laboratory Quality Assurance Unit at Animal & Plant Health Agency (APHA) were developed specifically for CARE and used to collect information and results from the participants.

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

The assigned contact persons were contacted by e-mail, and accounts were created, with personal log-on credentials for the reporting platform. The participants were further assigned an individual four digit identification number, and this number was used to identify the participants throughout the PT. On January 10 2022 an e-mail was dispatched to the contact persons containing a link that enabled the participants to upload their results the appropriate reporting platform. The three schemes were designated:

PT0513: Proficiency Test on Sequence Based Cluster Detection in *Campylobacter*
PT0514: Proficiency Test on Sequence Based Cluster Detection in *L. monocytogenes*
PT0510: Proficiency Test on Sequence Based Cluster Detection in *Salmonella*

The participants were asked to submit their results before 31 January 2022. A few of the participants asked for extra time to conduct the data analysis, and as a consequence the reporting platform were kept open until 28 February 2022. All reported data were exported and further analysed in Excel.

For each of the three schemes, all participants received individual feedback reports, where the results of the PT-provider were listed along with the submitted results. The report further listed the methods applied by both the PT-provider and the PT-participant. The individual reports were sent to the participants by e-mail May 23, 2022.

5.4. WGS analysis applied by the participants

For each bacterial scheme the participants were asked to provide general information about the applied methods used for the WGS analysis. The submitted information is presented in Table 2 for allele-based methods and in Table 3 for SNP-based methods.

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Table 2. Information about the applied methods and analytical approach from the PT-participants that used an allele-based approach.

Scheme	#Participant	Allele analysis tools	Allele calling method	Allele assembler used	Allele analysis scheme	Number of loci in allelic scheme	No. of allele differences used as cut-off for calling a cluster
<i>Campylobacter</i>	1226	BioNumerics	Both	SPAdes	wgMLST in BioNumerics	1343(core)	4
<i>Campylobacter</i>	2178	Bionumerics	Assembly based	Spades	cgMLSTOxford	1343	13
<i>Campylobacter</i>	2203	chewBBACA	Assembly based	SPAdes (inINNUca pipeline)	wgMLST ; http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1322564	2795	NA
<i>Campylobacter</i>	2544	SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes	C.jejuni/colicgMLSTscheme	637	13
<i>Campylobacter</i>	2675	Ridom SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes (assembled before importing to SeqSphere)	Campylobacterjejuni/coli cgMLST v1.3 byRidom	637	13
<i>Campylobacter</i>	3670	SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes	Oxford	1343	13
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	2544	SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes	L.monocytogenes cgMLST scheme	1701	10
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	2675	Ridom SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes (outside of SeqSphere soft ware suite)	L.monocytogenes cgMLST v2.1 by Ridom	1701	10
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	3700	BIGSdb-Lm	K-Mer based		Moura	1748	7
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	3721	SeqSphere+	Assembly bases	Unicycler	cgMLST (Ruppitsch scheme)	1701	4
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	3738	Ridom SeqSphere	Assembly based	Velvet	inhousescheme (by Finnish Institute for Health)	1053	7
<i>Salmonella</i>	1226	BioNumerics	Both	SPAdes	wgMLST BioNumerics	3002 (core)	3
<i>Salmonella</i>	2544	SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes	Salmonella enterica cgMLST scheme	3002	7
<i>Salmonella</i>	2675	Ridom SeqSphere	Assembly based	SPAdes (outside of SeqSphere software suite)	Salmonella enterica cgMLST v2.0 by Ridom	3002	7
<i>Salmonella</i>	2781	SeqSphere	Assembly based	Unicycler	Enterobase	3002	5
<i>Salmonella</i>	3311	chewBBACA	Assembly based	SPAdes	Enterobase cgMLST V2	3000	7
<i>Salmonella</i>	3359	chewBBACA BSR-Based Allele Call Alg (Galaxy V 2.0)	Assembly based	Spades	S Enterica cgMLST Enetropbase	2999	10
<i>Salmonella</i>	3640	Ridom SeqSphere v.7	Assembly based	Velvet	cgMLST (Enterobase)	3002	7

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Table 3. Information about the applied methods and analytical approach from the PT-participants that used a SNP-based approach.

Scheme	#Participant	Reference genome used	SNP pipeline	SNP analysis approach	SNP assembler	SNP variant caller	No. of SNP-differences used as cut-off for calling a cluster
<i>Campylobacter</i>	1657		In-house pipeline. Regarding Q1 the answer is index sample if applicable otherwise in-house or public reference depending of ST.	Reference based	CLC Assembly Cellv. 5.2	CLC Assembly Cellv. 5.2	10
<i>Campylobacter</i>	1880	CARE41, CARE52, CARE74, CARE63, CARE27, CARE60	Snippy	The fastq files were grouped according to their STs, Index samples were used as references after assembly for required ST groups, Snippy for full alignments, Gubbins to remove recombination sites, Snippy for core alignments and snp-dists for distance matrix.	Shovill for reference genome assembly.	Freebayes	5
<i>Campylobacter</i>	2648	NCTC11168	Inhouse	mapping to reference		bcftools	~14
<i>Campylobacter</i>	3722	Other sample isolates of the same ST	Whole genome SNP analysis	Pairwise whole genome alignment (Average Nucleotide Identity)	Velvet	Nucmer	35
<i>Campylobacter</i>	3763	CARE027	CSI phylogeny	Maximum Likelihood	SPAdes	CSI phylogeny	5
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	1657	1	Inhouse method. Regarding Q1 the answer is index sample if applicable otherwise in-house or public reference depending of ST.	Reference based	CLC Assembly Cell v.5.2	CLC Assembly Cell v.5.3	5
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	1880	CARE42, CARE39, CARE2, CARE44	Snippy	The fastq files were grouped according to their STs, Index samples were used as references after assembly for required ST groups, Snippy for full alignments, Gubbins to remove recombination sites, Snippy for core alignments and snp-dists for distance matrix	Shovill for assemble the reference genomes.	Freebayes	10
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	2648	EGD-e (NCBIGCA_000196035.1)	Inhouse	Mapping to reference		BCF tools	~7
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	3722	Other sample isolates of the same ST	Whole genome SNP analysis	Pairwise whole genome alignment (Average Nucleotide Identity)	Velvet	Nucmer	60
<i>L. monocytogenes</i>	3763	Care 002	CSI Phylogeny	Maximum likelihood	SPAdes	CSI Phylogeny	5
<i>Salmonella</i>	1657	Index sample, otherwise in-house or public reference depending of ST.	In house pipeline.	Reference based	CLC Assembly Cell v. 5.2	CLC Assembly Cell v. 5.2	5
<i>Salmonella</i>	1880	CARE86, CARE9, CARE11, CARE15.	Snippy - recombination removed using Gubbins	Index samples were used as references after assembly for required ST groups.	Shovill was used to assemble reference genomes	Freebayes	5
<i>Salmonella</i>	2235	CARE86 CARE9 CARE11 CARE15	snippy	cg SNP	SPAdes	Free bayes	450
<i>Salmonella</i>	2648	LT2 (NCBI: GCA_000006945)	in house	mapping to reference		BCFtools	~5
<i>Salmonella</i>	3670	Salmonella enterica LT2, accession nr NC_003197.2	In-house	Read mapping to reference genome	None (Bowtie2 for mapping)	BCFtools	3
<i>Salmonella</i>	3722	Other sample isolates of the same Serotype	Whole genome SNP analysis	Pairwise whole genome alignment (Average Nucleotide Identity)	Velvet	Nucmer	100
<i>Salmonella</i>	3763	Care086	CSI Phylogeny	Maximum likelihood	SPAdes	CSI Phylogeny	5

5.5. Data analysis

The results of QC, ST, species, serotype, and cluster calling from the PT-provider are presented in Table 4, 5 and 6 for *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*, respectively. The PT-providers results was based on the methods described previously (5.1 WGS analysis performed by the PT-provider). The cluster calling results reported by the participants are also presented in Table 4 to 6, which also contains information on the concordance of results provided by the participants compared to the results from the PT-provider. The concordance of results on QC, ST, species and serotype between the participants and the PT-provider are presented in Table 7. The number of allele- and/or SNP-differences reported are presented in Table 8, 9 and 10 for the *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* samples, respectively.

5.5.1. *Campylobacter* cluster assignment

The cluster calling results for the 35 *Campylobacter* sequences are presented in Table 4. The PT-provider identified three clusters, one major cluster consisting of 12 *C. jejuni*, ST257 isolates, a cluster that included two *C. coli* ST 872 isolates, and one cluster that included two *C. jejuni* ST 22 isolates.

Thirteen participants reported cluster results, of which eight applied an allele-based approach and five applied a SNP-based approach. A total of 375 concordant and 28 non-concordant results were reported. Six participants did not report data for all sequences, and 39 results were missing.

Four participants reported cluster results that all were in concordance with the PT-provider and in general the participants were able to identify the clusters. Non-concordant results were frequently reported for CARE052 and CARE097. These samples were both ST21 and exhibited a high degree of similarity. The PT-provider did not assign these two samples as a cluster as the applied cluster cut-off at 5 alleles/7 SNPs and analysis resulted in 7 alleles and 25 SNPs difference (See table 8). The participant that reported the highest number of non-concordant results were six.

Table 4. PT-providers *Campylobacter* results for QC, species, ST and cluster assignment and participants result for *Campylobacter* cluster assignment.

<i>Campylobacter</i>														No of concordant results	No of non-concordant results	No data reported				
Results from PT provider				Part of a cluster																
Sample#	QC passed	Species	ST#	Part of a cluster	Participant #															
CARE027	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	1226	1657	1880	2178	2203	2544	2648	2675	2781	3359	3670	3722	3763	12		1
CARE028	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														12		1
CARE029	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE030	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE031	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														12		1
CARE032	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														12		1
CARE033	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE034	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE035	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														12	1	
CARE036	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE037	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE038	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes														13		
CARE041	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No														9	4	
CARE043	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	860	No														9		4
CARE047	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	9765	No														7		6
CARE049	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	1628	No														9		4
CARE050	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	1624	No														9		4
CARE052	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No														7	5	1
CARE053	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No														10	3	
CARE055	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	No														11	2	
CARE057	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No														13		
CARE059	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	860	No														9		4
CARE060	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	872	Yes														11		2
CARE061	Yes	<i>C. coli</i>	872	Yes														12		1
CARE063	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No														9	4	
CARE065	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	122	No														8		5
CARE067	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No														12	1	
CARE068	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No														13		
CARE069	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No														11	2	
CARE073	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No														12		1
CARE074	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	22	Yes														11	1	1
CARE075	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	22	Yes														12		1
CARE080	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No														11	1	1
CARE097	Yes	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No														9	4	
CARE103	No	-	-	-																
No of concordant results					33	34	29	21	26	29	22	30	29	22	34	32	34	375		
No of non-concordant results					1	0	4	1	0	5	4	4	1	6	0	2	0		28	
No data reported					0	0	1	12	8	0	8	0	4	6	0	0	0			39

Clustering strains, concordant results
Clustering strains, concordant results
Clustering strains, concordant results
Non-concordant results
No data reported
Participant used SNP approach
Participant used allele based approach

5.5.2. *Listeria monocytogenes* cluster assignment

The cluster calling results for the 27 *L. monocytogenes* samples are presented in Table 5. The PT-provider identified one cluster consisting of eight *L. monocytogenes* ST 391 isolates.

Twelve participants reported cluster results for *L. monocytogenes*, of which seven applied an allele-based approach and five applied a SNP-based approach. A total of 278 concurring and 16 non-concurring results were reported. Four participants did not report data for all sequences. Two participants did not report 16 of the total of 18 missing results.

Five participants reported cluster results that all were in concordance with the PT-provider and in general the participants were able to identify the clusters. Among the non-concurring results CARE039, CARE042 and CARE044 were the samples most frequently reported as being part of cluster.

Table 4. PT-providers *Listeria monocytogenes* results for QC, ST and cluster assignment and participants result for *L. monocytogenes* cluster assignment.

<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>															No of concurring results	No of non-concurring results	No data reported	
Results from PT provider				Participant#														
Sample#	QC passed	ST#	Part of a cluster	1226	1657	1880	2544	2648	2675	3068	3700	3721	3722	3738				3763
CARE001	Yes	391	No													12		
CARE002	Yes	391	Yes													12		
CARE003	Yes	391	Yes													12		
CARE004	Yes	391	Yes													12		
CARE005	Yes	391	Yes													12		
CARE006	Yes	391	Yes													12		
CARE007	Yes	391	Yes													11	1	
CARE008	Yes	391	Yes													11		1
CARE039	Yes	8	No													8	4	
CARE040	Yes	1247	No													10		2
CARE042	Yes	1	No													9	3	
CARE044	Yes	451	No													8	4	
CARE045	Yes	8	No													11		1
CARE046	Yes	155	No													10		2
CARE051	Yes	1	No													12		
CARE054	Yes	782	No													10		2
CARE056	Yes	416	No													10		2
CARE058	Yes	37	No													10		2
CARE062	Yes	698	No													10		2
CARE064	Yes	451	No													11	1	
CARE066	Yes	155	No													10		2
CARE070	Yes	391	Yes													10	2	
CARE071	Yes	219	No													10		2
CARE072	Yes	1	No													12		
CARE077	Yes	8	No													12		
CARE098	Yes	451	No													11	1	
CARE104	No	-	-															
No of concurring results				26	26	23	22	17	26	15	24	26	22	26	25	278		
No of non-concurring results				0	0	3	3	1	0	3	2	0	3	0	1		16	
No data reported				0	0	0	1	8	0	8	0	0	1	0	0			18

	Clustering strains, concurring results
	Non-concurring results
	No data reported
	Participant used SNP approach
	Participant used allele based approach

5.5.3. *Salmonella* cluster assignment

The cluster calling results for the 31 *Salmonella* samples are presented in Table 6. The PT-provider identified two clusters, one major cluster consisting of nine samples of monophasic S. Typhimurium, ST34 isolates and one cluster with two S. Typhimurium ST19 isolates.

Fourteen participants reported *Salmonella* cluster results, of which seven applied an allele-based approach and seven applied a SNP-based approach. A total of 348 concordant and 44 non-concordant results were reported. Seven participants did not report data for all sequences, and in total 28 results were missing.

Two participant reported cluster results that all were all in concordance with the PT-provider and eight of the participants reported less than three non-concordant results. Two participants reported 15 and seven of the non-concordant results. Among the non-concordant results CARE009 and CARE99 caused eight and six of the non-concordant results, respectively. These two isolates were S. Enteritidis, ST11 and closely related but below the cut-off for cluster detection for some participants, see Table 10.

Table 5. PT-providers *Salmonella* results for QC, serotype, ST and cluster assignment and participants result for *Salmonella* cluster assignment.

		<i>Salmonella</i>															No of concording results	No of non- concording results	No data reported		
Results from PT provider				Part of a cluster																	
Sample#	QC passed	Serotype	ST#	Part of a cluster	Participant #																
					1226	1657	1880	2235	2544	2648	2675	2781	3311	3359	3640	3670	3722	3763			
CARE009	Yes	Enteritidis	11	No															6	8	0
CARE010	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															13	1	0
CARE011	Yes	Typhimurium	19	Yes															13	1	0
CARE012	Yes	Typhimurium	19	Yes															12	2	0
CARE013	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE014	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE015	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE016	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															11	2	1
CARE017	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE018	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															12	0	2
CARE019	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE020	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE021	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes															14	0	0
CARE022	Yes	Typhimurium	19	No															12	2	0
CARE023	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															12	2	0
CARE024	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															10	4	0
CARE025	Yes	Typhimurium	19	No															13	1	0
CARE026	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															13	1	0
CARE079	Yes	Stanley	29	No															10	0	4
CARE081	Yes	Kottbus	212	No															10	0	4
CARE082	Yes	Coeln	1995	No															8	2	4
CARE083	Yes	Typhimurium	36	No															10	0	4
CARE086	Yes	Dublin	10	No															10	4	0
CARE089	Yes	Dublin	10	No															12	2	0
CARE092	Yes	Enteritidis	11	No															14	0	0
CARE093	Yes	Dublin	10	No															12	2	0
CARE094	Yes	Coeln	1995	No															8	2	4
CARE095	Yes	4,5,12:i:-	34	No															12	2	0
CARE099	Yes	Enteritidis	11	No															7	6	1
CARE102	Yes	Agona	13	No															10	0	4
CARE105	No	-	-	-																	
No of concording results					28	28	29	15	27	24	29	28	22	20	27	22	19	30	348		
No of non-concording results					1	2	1	15	3	0	1	2	2	4	3	3	7	0		44	
No data reported					1	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	6	6	0	5	4	0			28

	Clustering strains, concording results
	Clustering strains, concording results
	Non-concording results
	No data reported
	Participant used SNP approach
	Participant used allele based approach

5.5.4. QC, species, serotype and ST

The concordance of participants reported and PT-provider results for QC, species, serotype- and STs are presented in Table 7.

Three samples did not pass the PT-providers QC pipeline. CARE103 from the *Campylobacter* scheme consisted of DNA from two different *Campylobacter* isolates, CARE104 from the *L. monocytogenes* scheme had a low read coverage and CARE105 from the *Salmonella* scheme was a *Salmonella* sequence contaminated with DNA from other species.

For *Campylobacter*, eight, eight and nine participants reported results for all isolates that were in concordance with the results from the PT-provider for QC, ST and species, respectively. A total of seven discrepancies were seen in QC reported by five participants and five results were missing. One species were incorrectly assigned and five species results were missing. All reported STs were in concordance with the expected results except for 11 not being reported.

For *L. monocytogenes*, 8 out of 12 participants reported results that were in concordance with the results from the PT-provider. A total of four discrepancies were seen for QC results and three participants did not report ST results for three sequences.

A total of eight participants reported *Salmonella* results in concordance with the results from the PT-provider. Two discrepancies were seen in reported QC-results and six were not reported. All reported STs were concurring although ST results from two participants were missing for five sequences. In total, seven serotype results were not reported by three different participants and three were not in concordance with the expected result.

5.5.5. Allele- and SNP-distances

The participants reported the allele- and SNP-difference for selected STs from all pathogens. These results and the results from the PT-provider are presented in Table 8, 9 and 10 for *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella*, respectively.

The reported allele- and SNP- differences were generally low for the clustering sequences, whereas difference were observed among the isolates that were more distantly related. A few participants did not report data for the index isolates and other did not report results for all samples. The reported number of allele differences were similar with a few exceptions (Table 8-10), e.g. participant #2178 that reported results on allele-differences that differed from the results of the PT-provider and the participants for *Campylobacter* (Table 8).

Participant #3700, that used a KMer based approach for for *L. monocytogenes* allele-analysis based on the Moura-method, (Table 2), reported results that were more than 100-fold different in comparison to results from the PT-provider and the participants. However, with the applied cluster cut-off value the participant were overall able to assign the cluster correctly (Table 5).

The *Salmonella* participants reported very similar results on allele-differences (Table 10)

In general, a prominent difference were observed among the participants that used SNP-based method and differences were also observed in the results from the PT-provider, when the same isolates were analyzed with different tools (CleanRecomb, ClonalFrame, Gubbins) for removal of recombination. Especially removal of recombination effected the number of SNP-differences in *Campylobacter* and approximately 400-fold differences were seen in SNP-differences when using CleanRecomb and ClonalFrame (Table 8).

Table 6. Concordance of reported QC, ST, *Campylobacter* species, and *Salmonella* serotypes between PT-provider and participants.

Concording/non-concording/no results					
Species	Laboratory #	Quality Control	Sequence Type	Species	Serotype
Campylobacter	1226	35/0/0	33/0/1	34/0/0	
	1657	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	1880	34/1/0	33/0/1	32/1/1	
	2178	31/2/2	30/0/2	32/0/2	
	2203	33/2/0	30/0/2	32/0/2	
	2544	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	2648	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	2675	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	2781	31/1/3	29/0/5	30/0/0	
	3359	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	3670	34/1/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	3722	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
	3763	35/0/0	34/0/0	34/0/0	
L. monocytogenes	1226	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	1657	27/0/0	25/0/1		
	1880	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	2544	26/1/0	25/0/1		
	2648	26/1/0	26/0/0		
	2675	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	3068	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	3700	26/1/0	26/0/0		
	3721	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	3722	26/1/0	25/0/1		
	3738	27/0/0	26/0/0		
	3763	27/0/0	26/0/0		
Salmonella	1226	30/1/0	29/0/1		28/1/1
	1657	30/1/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	1880	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	2235	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	2544	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	2648	30/0/1	30/0/0		30/0/0
	2675	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	2781	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	3311	31/0/0	30/0/0		26/2/2
	3359	30/0/1	30/0/0		30/0/0
	3640	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	3670	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0
	3722	27/0/4	26/0/4		26/0/4
3763	31/0/0	30/0/0		30/0/0	

Table 7. *Campylobacter* allele- and SNP-differences reported by participants and PT-provider. The assigned index isolates are marked with yellow. Empty cells indicate that no results were reported.

<i>Campylobacter</i>																					
Samples				Allele-differences/participant									SNP-differences/participant								
Samples	Species	ST#	Part of a cluster	Allele-differences/participant									SNP-differences/participant								
				#1226	#2178	#2203	#2544	#2675	#2781	#3359	#3545	PT-provider	#1226	#1657	#1880	#2648	#3722	#3763	CleanRecomb/PT-provider	ClonalFrame/PT provider	Gubbins/PT provider
CARE027	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CARE028	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	1	1		0	1	3	7	2	1	1	8	0	0	15	0	1	0	
CARE029	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	1	5	0	0	20	0	1	0	
CARE030	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	0	0	1	0	1	3	1	2	0	1	5	0	0	16	0	1	0	
CARE031	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	1		1	0	1	3	0	1	1	1	8	0	0	27	0	1	0	
CARE032	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	2	1		0	2	4	2	5	2	2	5	1	0	17	1	2	1	
CARE033	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	2	1	3	1	2	5	2	4	2	6	16	5	1	25	7	5	4	
CARE034	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	1	1	1	0	1	3	2	2	1	1	9	0	0	13	0	1	0	
CARE035	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	5	1	4	2	3	7	5	6	5	8	19	7	1	18	9	5	6	
CARE036	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	2	1	3	1	2	5	5	5	2	6	16	5	1	24	7	5	4	
CARE037	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	2	0	3	1	3	6	4	5	2	6	14	5	1	17	7	5	4	
CARE038	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	Yes	1	1	1	0	1	3	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	10	0	1	0	
CARE060	<i>C. coli</i>	872	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CARE061	<i>C. coli</i>	872	Yes	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	2		22	2	2	2	
CARE074	<i>C. jejuni</i>	22	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CARE075	<i>C. jejuni</i>	22	Yes	0	0	1	0	0		0	3	0	0	0	1	0	11	0	0	0	
CARE041	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No	0	200	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CARE052	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
CARE053	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No	548	200	454	277	277	592	243		548	6638	7041	527	213	2668	3812	6638	19	535
CARE055	<i>C. jejuni</i>	257	No	34	26	37	14	15	34	4		34	892	1099	28	9	227	377	892	14	29
CARE057	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No	282	200	220	133	133	420	26		282	3208	4086	108	147	1253	1570	1160	88	257
CARE063	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No	0	200	0	0	0	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE067	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No	278	200	215	127	128	298	4		278	3115	3755	107	139	1139	1476	1173	85	255
CARE068	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No	713	200	561	342	343	1040	452		713	8762	9688	816	233	3476	4954	1169	103	1303
CARE069	<i>C. jejuni</i>	19	No	548	200	455	279	279	607	107		548	6639	6896	526	217	2654	3814	6639	17	537
CARE073	<i>C. jejuni</i>	50	No	272	200	211	119	119		27		272	3110	3965	103	133	1243	1489	1189	86	256
CARE080	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No	179	165	138	8	84	219	12		179	1936	2161	99	213	803	1064	532	24	94
CARE097	<i>C. jejuni</i>	21	No	25	25	21	11	11	32	0		25	590	534	6	217	164	274	77	23	7

Table 8. *Listeria monocytogenes* allele- and SNP-differences reported by participants and PT-provider. The assigned index isolates are marked with yellow. Empty cells indicate that no results were reported.

<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>																		
Samples			Allele-differences/participant							SNP-differences/participant								
Sample#	ST#	Part of a cluster	#1226	#2544	#2675	#3068	#3700	#3721	#3738	Provider	#1226	#1657	#1880	#2648	#3763	CleanRecomb/PT-provider	ClonalFrame/PT provider	Gubbins/PT provider
CARE002	391	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE003	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
CARE004	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
CARE005	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
CARE006	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
CARE007	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	44	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
CARE008	391	Yes	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	3	0	5	2	2	5	5
CARE070	391	Yes	4	3	3	3	316	3	2	4	5	5	5	1	11	5	4	5
CARE001	391	No	52	47	47	47	52	47	35	52	580	90	95	26	237	580	13	97
CARE039	8	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE042	1	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE044	451	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE045	8	No	22	19	18	19	148	19	18	22	665	52	39	174	185	39	52	52
CARE051	1	No	73	75	75	75	108	75	61	73	166	159	164	95	158	166	22	165
CARE064	451	No	28	26	26	37	95	25	20	28	48	1115	49	29	48	48	16	50
CARE072	1	No	119	116	116	185	211	116	81	119	245	251	245	147	269	245	23	262
CARE077	8	No	30	26	26	38	106	26	26	30	1113	1646	58	44	306	207	40	62
CARE098	451	No	16	19	19	19	75	19	16	16	31	34	32	21	33	31	14	33

Table 9. *Salmonella* allele- and SNP-differences reported by participants and PT-provider. The assigned index isolates are marked with yellow. Empty cells indicate that no results were reported.

<i>Salmonella</i>																						
Samples				Allele-differences/participant								SNP-differences/participant										
Sample#	Serotype	ST#	Part of a cluster	#1226	#2544	#2675	#2781	#3311	#3359	#3640	Provider	#1226	#1657	#1880	#2235	#2648	#3670	#3722	#3763	CleanRecomb/PT-provider	ClonalFrame/PT provider	Gubbins/PT provider
CARE011	Typhimurium	19	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE012	Typhimurium	19	Yes	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	2	6	2	4	2	5	29	1	2	2	2
CARE013	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	4	4	0	30	0	0	0	0
CARE014	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0
CARE015	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE017	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	4	0	42	0	0	0	0
CARE018	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	1	3	1	3	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE019	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	2	0	46	0	0	0	0
CARE020	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6	3	0	47	0	0	0	0
CARE021	4,5,12:i:-	34	Yes	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	4	5	0	37	0	0	0	0
CARE009	Enteritidis	11	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE010	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	17	16	16	15	15	15	15	17	198	396	33	184	17	36	120	154	22	18	26
CARE016	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	11	11	11	10	10	10	9	11	16	16	21	17	43	21	17	16	9	21	
CARE022	Typhimurium	19	No	312	316	315	434	318	305	313	312	1002	1555	675	1044	567	786	884	799	771	29	690
CARE023	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	21	21	20	20	20	20	19	21	23	40	28	66	196	30	68	39	23	10	30
CARE024	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	8	8	8	8	8	9	7	8	11	26	17	18	63	16	47	24	11	6	15
CARE025	Typhimurium	19	No	247	253	253	253	253	244	242	247	1022	1551	556	917	452	635	698	696	680	31	569
CARE026	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	24	24	24	24	24	24	23	24	348	655	53	395	37	52	221	314	32	18	53
CARE086	Dublin	10	No	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CARE089	Dublin	10	No	182	171	171	185	179	134	166	182	418	413	373	425	545	342	400	386	335	24	378
CARE092	Enteritidis	11	No	208	210	210	209	214	212	203	208	463	441	459	473	609	431	471	457	463	16	458
CARE093	Dublin	10	No	24	168	167	166	173	141	162	176	362	334	366	377	562	330	379	358	329	19	369
CARE095	4,5,12:i:-	34	No	9	9	9	9	8	7	8	9	14	22	16	33	26	16	54	30	14	6	18
CARE099	Enteritidis	11	No	4	5	5	4	4	6	4	4	16	17	19	23	265	14	16	16	9	17	

6. Discussion including concluding remarks

In this cross-sectorial in silico based PT, the participants representing the public health, veterinary and food sector, were asked to analyse genome sequences (FASTQ format) generated from *Campylobacter*, *L. monocytogenes* and *Salmonella* isolates. The participants were asked to use their current WGS pipeline for analysis of the samples. The participants were asked to evaluate the quality of the genome sequences and for sequences with a satisfactory quality the participants should extract the ST, species for *Campylobacter* and serotype for *Salmonella*. The participants were also asked to identify samples clustering together and to report allele- and/or SNP- differences to predefined index samples. Additionally the participants were asked to provide information on their analytical approach and software used. The participants results were compared to the results from the PT-provider, and feedback on the concordance of results were provided individually to each of the participants.

Most participants were able to correctly determine the quality of the genome sequences provided and further to identify the correct species, serotype and ST from the sequences.

In general, the participants were able to identify the clusters of closely related samples, in concordance with the results generated by the PT-provider and there was no obvious cross-sectorial

differences observed. The participants provided information about the methods used for cluster detection and approximately half applied an allele-based approach and half a SNP-based approach (Table 1). For both approaches the participants reported the use of a wide range of different tools for their analytical approach (Table 2 and 3) and the participants also reported diverging cut-off values for cluster assignment. Some of the discrepancies seen in the cluster assignments (Table 4-6) could be explained by the use of different cut-off values, an example being the two closely related *S. Enteritidis* mentioned earlier (paragraph on *Salmonella* cluster assignment). The results from this PT shows that cut-off values for cluster assignment is of major importance in future harmonization work.

In the present PT the participants had the freedom to choose their analytical approach and one very important conclusion of the study is, that the methods that are being used overall are able to identify the same clusters for all three species.

A major observation of the study was that the use of different tools for removal of recombination are affecting the results of the number of identified SNP-differences when the same genome sequences are analysed. But it is also clear that the purpose of identifying the correct clusters are fulfilled independently of the tools used for removal of recombination. However, it is advised that the use of different recombination tools is an area that needs to be visited in the future harmonization of methods for cluster detection.

The execution of the current PT was cumbersome for both the PT-provider and participants. The selection and characterization of PT-samples and the distribution of genome sequences worked really well, but the reporting and feedback procedure could be improved. The customized version of the APHA platform used for reporting were dependent of the participants manually uploaded their information and results, and likewise there were a lot of manual work in the preparation of the feedback reports to the participants and finalizing the present final report. All manual handling of data is associated with a risk of including human errors. Based on the experiences from the current PT it is recommended that automatized platforms are developed, as these can facilitate the up- and download of PT-results and improve the data analysis of cluster detection PTs both with regard to time and manpower.

In the present pilot PT there were not set any criteria for evaluation of the participants performance. But the requirements for "passing" an *in silico* based genome sequence PT for cluster detection should be considered in future work.

An important conclusion from this pilot PT is that it is possible to use a cross-sectoral approach for assessment of the One Health capacity to characterise and detect clusters among food-borne pathogens based on WGS. The further development of WGS based cluster detection PTs requires a multidisciplinary approach and require skills from the laboratory side as well as programming and computational skills. It is important that the work is undertaken internationally so it is ensured that the new tools are applicable worldwide, It is further important, that the responsible national and international bodies are supporting the area with resources in order to facility the development of methodologies and harmonization of the area. Once the PTs are in place it will be easy to conduct cross sectorial one-health based PTs as this only will require that the laboratories from the different sectors sign up for the same PTs.

7. Acknowledgements

The institutions listed below participated in the pilot PT. The contact persons and their colleagues are acknowledged for their participation in this pilot PT.

This task is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.

Name of contact person(s)	Institution
Angela van Hoek	RIVM, the Netherlands
Anniina Jaakkonen	Finnish Food Authority
Ásgeir Ástvaldsson	SVA, National Veterinary Institute, Sweden
Chng Kern Rei and Lim Jia Qi	Singapore Food Agency
Gianni Ciccaglioni	Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy
Jette Sejer Kjeldgaard	DTU - National Food Institute, Denmark
Joakim Skarin	Swedish Food Agency
Juris Kibilds	Institute of Food Safety, "BIOR", Spain
Laetitia Bonifait	ANSES Ploufragan, France
Laura Villa	Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Italy
Liljana Petrovska	Animal & Plant Health Agency, United Kingdom
Magdalena Zajac	PIWET, Poland
Malgorzata Ligowska-Marzeta	Statens Serum Institut, Denmark
Maroua Sayeb	ANSES Ploufragan, France
Nadja Karamehmedovic	Public Health Agency of Sweden
Raquel Abad Torreblanca	Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Spain
Silvia Herrera León	Instituto de Salud Carlos III, Spain
Suvi Wallgren	Finnish Food Authority
Taru Lienemann	Finnish Food Authority
Valérie Rose	ANSES Laboratory for Food Safety, France